

MCAA Call to Minimise the Impact of Brexit on Research

Statement by the Marie Curie Alumni Association (MCAA)

The [Marie Curie Alumni Association](#) (MCAA) has been following the evolution of the Brexit negotiations with major concern. We join the broader scientific community in emphasising that it is imperative for the UK, and to some extent for the ERA, that research and innovation cooperation programmes between the UK and the EU are maintained after Brexit. Independent of the scenario that plays out, the MCAA urges that the British government prioritizes association to Horizon Europe and unrestricted UK-EU mobility for researchers.

Historically, the UK has been a major recipient of European research funding. Within Horizon 2020 (2014-2020), the UK has been awarded to date €5.1 billion (14.35% of the total allocations). MSCA grants awarded to UK organisations total €768 million, distributed among 770 UK organisations. The Universities of Cambridge and Oxford, and University College London top the list with more than €40 million received through MSCA grants each. In addition to academic institutions, small and medium enterprises have also benefited from MSCA funds with companies like Ludger Limited (Abingdon) and AvantiCell Science Ltd (Ayr) receiving €1.3 million each. These grants constitute valuable opportunities for fellows and institutions, and provide intangible benefits such as long-term collaborations and links for future partnerships.

The UK has also been a main host country for highly qualified researchers from Horizon 2020 programs, with 1673 individual fellows moving to work at UK institutions and receiving salaries from MSCA funding. In addition, UK organisations have participated 1346 times in Innovative Training Networks, which finance PhD students and young researchers. The MSCA programme has also funded 993 UK researchers to develop their careers internationally or reintegrate after a period abroad. This mobility has been a driving force for research and innovation in the UK.

About MCAA

The [Marie Curie Alumni Association](#) (MCAA) is a global network open to any past or present researchers supported by the [Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions](#) (MSCA). MSCA is one of the European Union's flagship training initiatives and provides research grants supporting researcher's international and intersectoral mobility at all stages of their careers, across all disciplines. MSCA fellowships are among Europe's most competitive and prestigious awards, aimed to support the best, most promising researchers.

Data from:

<https://webgate.ec.europa.eu/dashboard/sense/app/93297a69-09fd-4ef5-889f-b83c4e21d33e>

https://ec.europa.eu/research/mariecurieactions/sites/mariecurie2/files/msca-country-profile-unitedkingdom-2018_en_0.pdf

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Policy
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